

Local Government in Switzerland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Switzerland: An Introduction

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The Swiss Federal Constitution provides in its Article 50 that the autonomy of the communes is guaranteed in accordance with cantonal law and that the Confederation shall take account in its activities of the possible consequences for the municipalities. In doing so, it shall take account of the special position of the cities and urban areas as well as mountain regions. This provision does not provide the Confederation with additional competence over the municipalities but rather invites the three institutional levels to intensify the vertical dialogues and to cooperate more efficiently.

In Switzerland, cantonal constitutions and statutory laws govern the legal frameworks in which municipalities operate. Therefore, the federal system is very heterogeneous, and it is difficult to have a clear picture of the municipalities' competencies in all 26 Swiss cantons. One would have to study carefully the legislation of each specific canton to define the degree of autonomy held by each municipality.

The academic literature confirms one general conclusion: the French-speaking cantons tend to be more centralized than the German-speaking cantons.⁸ Scholars also point out that, for historical and geographical reasons, municipalities in the Canton of Grisons/Graubünden exercise a high degree of autonomy, while those in the cantons of Basel-City and Geneva enjoy relatively limited self-determination. In fact, the latter two cantons are sometimes called 'canton-city'⁹ because of the small number of municipalities and the strong interdependence between the city and the canton. While the Canton of Basel was split in two half-cantons in 1833 (Basel-City and Basel-Country; the former being composed of only 3 municipalities), the Canton of Geneva has 40 municipalities and discussions to merge the municipalities with the Canton of Geneva come up regularly.

Therefore, in general terms municipalities enjoy what can be called a residual autonomy although the precise terminology differs from one canton to the other. They are competent when the local tasks are neither incumbent on the confederation nor on the canton.¹⁰ Among them, taxation, policing, land planning, public roads, environment protection, public education, social aid, naturalization and culture typically lies in the hands of the municipalities although it is not an exclusive competence but usually shared with the cantons and often only

⁸ Stéphane Grodecki, 'Les compétences communales – comparaison intercantonale' in Thierry Tanquerel and François Bellanger (eds), *L'avenir juridique des communes* (Schulthess 2007) 74.

⁹ *ibid* 74.

¹⁰ *ibid* 28, 29.

executed by the municipalities. Of all of them, culture is probably the policy field in which municipalities have the most leeway.¹¹

As the Swiss federal system typically is the result of independent states coming together to form a confederation, there is certainly no uniform scheme of responsibilities throughout the country. Competencies in the policy fields listed above are neither distributed according to clear criteria nor according to the capabilities of the municipalities, whether rural or urban.

Interestingly, the relative broad municipal autonomy allows them to outsource some services to the private sector, including policing which of course calls into question the monopoly of the state for sovereign issues and challenges the democratic control over security forces.¹²

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Guerry M, 'La privatisation de la sécurité et ses limites juridiques' (2006) 2 La Semaine judiciaire 141

Grodecki S, 'Les compétences communales – comparaison intercantonale' in Thierry Tanquerel and François Bellanger (eds), *L'avenir juridique des communes* (Schulthess 2007)

¹¹ Grodecki, 'Les compétences communales', above, 74.

¹² Michael Guerry, 'La privatisation de la sécurité et ses limites juridiques' (2006) 2 La Semaine judiciaire 141.

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